

Studies on the Oxidation of Mandelic acid by Meta-periodic acid

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It has been found possible to estimate mandelic acid quantitatively by meta-periodic acid at 30° within a time limit of 20 hrs at pH~8 using, at least, three equivalents of periodate as against the reported oxidation at 100°. The reaction has been shown to be of the second order. The temperature coefficient was found to be of the order of 2.33 for the temperature range 35-45° and the energy of activation was 16.45 k. cal./mole at pH~6. The studies on the effect of added sulphate and acetate ions showed that there is an inhibiting salt effect and that the reaction takes place between periodate ion (theoretically $\text{IO}_4^- + \text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{--}$ ions) and mandelate ion as shown by the fact that the observed value of the rate constants becomes maximum at pH~8 similar to the product of calculated values of $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CHOHCOO}^-]$ $[\text{IO}_4^- + \text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{--}]$ ions. The reaction is acid catalysed, and the C—C bond fission is indicative of analogy with the oxidation of glycol or pinacol by periodate.

A survey of the literature revealed¹⁻⁴ that some work^{5,6} seems to have been done on the oxidation of mandelic acid by periodic acid at 100°. However, no work appears to have been done on the kinetics of the oxidation of mandelic acid by meta-periodic acid. Here, an attempt has been made to study the estimation of mandelic acid by periodate and also the influence of pH on the above reaction and elucidate its reaction mechanism. The reaction takes place as follows:—

EXPERIMENTAL

Determination of excess Periodate: Mandelic acid, sodium meta-periodate and other chemicals used were B. D. H. AnalaR products and were used without any further purification. To 15 ml. of standardised periodate solution (0.05 *N*) in a conical stoppered flask were added 10-15 ml. of a buffer (containing Na_2HPO_4 and borax solutions (0.1 *M*) mixed in the ratio 5:1). A definite volume, say 5 ml. (0.05 *N*) of mandelic acid (to be estimated) was added and the flask kept aside at 30° for 20 hr with occasional stirring. After the required time, 5-10 ml. of saturated sodium bicarbonate solution, 1 ml. of 20% potassium iodide and 20 ml. of standard 0.05 *N* arsenite solution (5 ml. in excess of periodate reagent taken) were added, and the flask kept aside for, at least, 15 minutes. During this time arsenite solution reacted with its equivalent of periodate, leaving only the excess arsenite unreacted. The excess arsenite solution was titrated with standard

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0.05*N* iodine solution. Blanks were simultaneously run with the same quantities of reagents (minus the substance to be oxidised). From the values of the two titres, the volume of the reagent used in the oxidation of mandelic acid could be known.

Table I gives the results obtained in the estimation of mandelic acid by periodate.

Estimation of mandelic acid: The prepared mandelic acid solution contains 0.9500 gms. of it/250 ml. as standardised by titration against standard alkali solution. Periodate was standardised against standard arsenious oxide solution.

1ml. of 0.05 *N* $\text{HIO}_4 \equiv 0.00380$ gms. mandelic acid.

TABLE I

All reagents—0.05 N; pH~8.
Time=20 hours, Temperature=30°

No.	Mandelic acid (0.05 N) added (ml)	Periodic acid (0.05 N) taken (ml.)	Arsenite (0.05N) added (ml.)	Periodic acid (0.05 N) used (ml.)	Mandelic acid taken (gms.)	Mandelic acid found (gms.)	% Recovery	% Error
1.	5.00	5.00	10.00	2.90	0.01900	0.01102	52.73	incomplete.
2.	5.00	10.00	15.00	3.90	0.01900	0.01482	78.00	incomplete.
3.	5.00	15.00	20.00	5.03	0.01900	0.01911	100.57	+0.57
4.	5.00	15.00	20.00	5.01	0.01900	0.01903	100.16	+0.16
5.	6.00	20.00	25.00	6.02	0.02280	0.02287	100.30	+0.30
6.	8.00	25.00	30.00	8.02	0.03040	0.03047	100.23	+0.23
7.	10.00	30.00	35.00	10.03	0.03800	0.03811	100.29	+0.29
8.	12.00	40.00	45.00	12.02	0.04560	0.04567	100.15	+0.15

Kinetic study of the reaction between mandelic acid and metaperiodic acid: For kinetic studies on the effect of *pH* and temperature, the following procedure was adopted: To 25 ml. of 0.025*N* meta-periodic acid was added the requisite quantity of buffer solution. After keeping it for half-an-hour in the constant temperature bath, 25 ml. of 0.025 *N* mandelic acid (which had been kept at the same temperature of the bath for about half-an-hour) was added to it and volume made up to 100 ml. The timer was started during the mixing. Samples (10 ml.) were removed at known intervals of time and quenched in 5-10 ml. of a saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate containing 1 ml. of 5% potassium iodide to which 15 ml. of 0.005 *N* arsenite had been added. The excess arsenite was titrated with 0.005 *N* iodine solution after keeping it for 15 minutes.

Reaction Rates: Graphs were plotted for all results and the specific reaction constants k_1 (first order) (figure I) and k_2 (second order) (figures II to V). obtained from the slope of $\log(a-x)$ and $1/(a-x)$ respectively against time. The value of k_2 , thus, obtained is, then, multiplied by a factor V/S where "V" is the volume of the reaction mixture analysed every time (here, 10 ml.) and "S" is the strength of the iodine solution. This is the absolute value of k_2 . In all graphs, "a" stands for the amount of periodate taken and "x" for periodate consumed in terms of the titre values of 0.005*N* iodine solution (with which the final titrations were carried out) required for 10 ml. of the reaction mixture.

The corresponding values of k_2 at varying pH values at $45^\circ \pm 0.1$ are tabulated below :

TABLE II

Temperature = $45 \pm 0.1^\circ$

No.	Mean pH	k_2 (Second order constants)	k (hour. ⁻¹ mole. ⁻¹ litre.)
1.	2.15	0.00308	12.32
2.	3.95	0.00233	9.32
3.	6.00	0.00287	11.48
4.	8.10	0.01329	53.16
5.	10.00	0.00189	7.56
6.	12.05	0.00141	5.64

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As against the reported oxidation of mandelic acid by meta-periodic acid at 100° , it has been found that mandelic acid can be quantitatively oxidised by metaperiodic acid at 30° within a time limit of 20 hrs. at $pH \sim 8$ using an excess (at least three equivalents) of periodate, otherwise the reaction is not complete even after 20 hrs.

FIG. 1

First order constants at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$

(Effect of increasing mandelic acid concentration)

pH	Periodate	Mandelic acid	Curve	k_1 ($\text{min}^{-1} \times 10^{-3}$)
2.30	$3.125 \times 10^{-3}M$	$62.5 \times 10^{-3}M$	A	1.17
2.25	$3.125 \times 10^{-3}M$	$125 \times 10^{-3}M$	B	2.26
2.15	$3.125 \times 10^{-3}M$	$187.5 \times 10^{-3}M$	C	3.80

In case of studies with increasing concentrations of mandelic acid, the time required for the completion of the reaction was inversely proportional to initial concentrations (figure I A, B and C) which showed that the overall order of reaction was two which was further confirmed by the results obtained on studies of second order constants using equal concentrations of reactants (figures II to V) where a straight line was obtained by plotting the values of $1/(a-x)$ against time in hours. The temperature coefficient was found to be of the order of 2.33 for the temperature range 35° - 45° and the energy of activation was 16.45 k. cal/mole at $pH \sim 6$. The studies on the effect of addition of sulphate (figure IIB)

and acetate ions (figure IIC) showed that there is an inhibiting salt effect and that reaction takes place between periodate ion (theoretically IO_4^- and $\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{3-}$ ions) and mandelate ion.

FIG. II

Second order constants at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$
(Effect of addition of ions)

pH	Periodate	Mandelic acid	Curve	k_2 (hour ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹ , litre)
2.15	$3.125 \times 10^{-3}\text{M}$	$3.125 \times 10^{-3}\text{M}$	A	6.16
2.05	„ „	„ „	B	5.28 (In presence of SO_4^{2-})
2.15	„ „	„ „	C	4.88 (In presence of CH_3COO^-)

FIG. III

Second order constants at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$

pH	Periodate	Mandelic acid	Curve	k_2 (hours ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹ litre)
3.75	$3.125 \times 10^{-3}\text{M}$	$3.125 \times 10^{-3}\text{M}$	D	8.92 (Solvent=50% NN dimethyl Formamide)
4.05	„ „	„ „	E	3.92
6.10	„ „	„ „	F	4.92
7.85	„ „	„ „	G	8.04

The summarised results on the effect of pH on reaction rates at 35° are tabulated below alongwith the calculated values of

FIG. IV

pH	Second order constants at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$		Curve	k_2 (hour ⁻¹ , mole ⁻¹ litre)
	Periodate	Mandelic acid		
8.15	$3.125 \times 10^{-3} M$	$3.125 \times 10^{-3} M$	H	9.00
8.90	" "	" "	I	3.92

FIG. V.

pH	Second order constants at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$		Curve	k_2 (hour ⁻¹ , mole ⁻¹ litre)
	Periodate	Mandelic acid		
10.00	$3.125 \times 10^{-3} M$	$3.125 \times 10^{-3} M$	J	3.64
11.95	" "	" "	K	3.56

Calculations in the concentrations of H_5IO_6 , $[H_4IO_6^-]$, $[IO_4^-]$ and $[H_3IO_6^{--}]$ present in periodic acid solution with change of pH were carried out with the acid of the following equilibria^{7,8} at 25° .

Similarly, for calculating the concentrations of mandelic acid molecule, $[C_6H_5CHOHCOOH]$, and mandelate ion, $[C_6H_5CHOHCOO^-]$, the following equilibrium has been employed.

$$\frac{[H^+] \times [C_6H_5CHOHCOO^-]}{[C_6H_5CHOHCOOH]} = 1.4 \times 10^{-4} \quad (\text{at } 25^\circ)$$

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TABLE III(A)

Calculated concentrations of the components in the reaction mixture at the middle stage of the reaction

No.	pH	(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)
		$[C_6H_5CHOCOOH]$ $[(10_4)^- + (H_3IO_6)^-] \times 2$	$[C_6H_5CHOHCOOH]$ $[(H_4IO_6)^- + (H_3IO_6)^-] \times 2$	$[C_6H_5CHOHCOO]$ $[(IO_4)^- + (H_3IO_6)^-] \times 0.5$	$[C_6H_5CHOHCOO]$ $[(H_4IO_6)^- + (H_3IO_6)^-] \times 0.5$
1.	2	20.65×10^{-4}	48.12×10^{-6}	0.37×10^{-5}	0.01×10^{-5}
2.	4	17.88×10^{-4}	40.58×10^{-6}	31.28×10^{-5}	0.70×10^{-5}
3.	6	0.59×10^{-4}	1.16×10^{-6}	70.45×10^{-5}	1.91×10^{-5}
4.	8	0.31×10^{-6}	0.10×10^{-6}	71.50×10^{-5}	23.37×10^{-5}
5.	10	0.29×10^{-6}	0.29×10^{-6}	69.65×10^{-5}	68.20×10^{-5}
6.	12	0.30×10^{-6}	0.30×10^{-6}	69.55×10^{-5}	69.59×10^{-5}

The following table gives the observed values of the second order constants of the reaction between mandelic acid and metaperiodic acid at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$ (Figures II(A), III(E), III(F), III(G), IV(H), IV(I), and V(J)).

TABLE III(B)

Observed values of second order rate constants.

No.	Initial pH	Final pH	Mean pH	k	
				K_2 (second order constants) $hour^{-1}$	$mole^{-1} litre.$
1.	2.20	2.10	2.15	0.00154	6.16
2.	4.10	4.00	4.05	0.00098	3.92
3.	6.20	6.00	6.10	0.00123	4.92
4.	7.90	7.80	7.85	0.00201	8.04
5.	8.20	8.10	8.15	0.00225	9.00
6.	9.00	8.80	8.90	0.00098	3.92
7.	10.10	9.90	10.00	0.00091	3.64
8.	12.00	11.90	11.95	0.00089	3.56

A perusal of the above table shows that the reaction rate is maximum at $pH \sim 8.1 - 8.3$ and on the both sides of this value, the rate appears to slow down but again improves at $pH 2.1-2.2$. It appears that the periodate ion (theoretically $IO_4^- + H_3IO_6^-$ ions) is the main reactive species at $pH \sim 8$ and that the reaction is acid catalysed. The product of calculated values of $[(IO_4)^- + (H_3IO_6)^-] [C_6H_5CHOHCOO]^-$ like the observed value of rate constant is maximum at $pH \sim 8$. This shows that $[(IO_4)^- + (H_3IO_6)^-]$ might be the reactive species in this case.

Mechanism :— The operative mechanism is decided by the comparative chelating nature of the substrate and the medium. The speeding up of the reaction in a medium of 50% dimethyl formamide (figure IIID) shows that periodate ion which is greatly chelated with dimethyl formamide will preferentially chelate with mandelate ion. The reaction can be represented as follows:—

Here, a complex formation is involved in the system and C-C bond fission is indicated by the production of CO_2 . The formation of an aldehyde suggests that the alcoholic course of oxidation is also operative. On the basis of C-C bond fission, the present reaction should be analogous to the oxidation of glycols or pinacol where C-C bond fission is an established fact. The production of an aldehyde in the reaction system points out that the reaction adopts and exhibits similarity with the oxidation of alcohols.

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